

Supplementary figures and tables

Supplementary Figure 1. A) Experimental design of the INDIGO study. GD patients (newly diagnosed/relapse untreated or within 6-weeks treatments with anti-thyroid drugs (ATD)) and GO patients (also euthyroid) enrolled in the study should have provided biological samples (blood, tears, nasal swab and feces) at the time of recruitment (baseline), at a second evaluation's visit (after initiating or continuing ATD) and after 6 months of ATD withdrawal/relapse of the disease, ideally in 18-months' time from recruitment. Exclusion criteria included ATD usage for more than 6 weeks and antibiotics intake in the past 3 months, at least. B) Alpha diversity indices of richness (Chao1 and observed OTUs), diversity (Shannon) and equitability of both patients and controls gut microbiota across centres. C) Non-metric dimensional scaling (NMDS) based on the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrix showed some spatial differences amongst nations. PERMANOVA $P=0.02$ with 999 permutations. D) Phylum distribution across nations of recruitment. Differences were observed in terms of Firmicutes and Proteobacteria counts. P-values generated with pairwise t-test and Benjamini-Hochberg (FDR) correction.

Supplementary Figure 2. Bacterial genera were differentially abundant amongst diagnosis groups (GD, GO and controls). Heatmap of the median value of each genus per group, scaled according to the row Z-score. Only significant genera with $P < 0.05$ from the linear regression model are shown; pairwise post-hoc with Benjamini-Hochberg (FDR) correction tests between groups are shown in the bar-plots. §: Genera included in the variable importance from the Random Forest model.

Supplementary figure 3. Gut microbiota composition associated with thyroid status (euthyroid-controls, hyperthyroid patients, hypothyroid patients and euthyroid patients). A) Non-metric dimensional scaling (NMDS) plot based on the Bray-Curtis dissimilarity matrix according to the thyroid status. Overall PERMANOVA based on 999 permutations P=0.02. Only one patient was hypothyroid due to anti-thyroid treatment and was removed from further analysis. B) Bootstrapped distribution of the Firmicutes:Bacteroidetes ratio from 500 replicates of the dataset for euthyroid vs. hyperthyroid samples (irrespective of the initial diagnosis). C) *Fusicatenibacter* spp. relative abundances according to thyroid status. D) *Bacteroides* spp. relative abundances according to thyroid status. E) Random Forest confusion matrix with the per-class classification for thyroid status groups. Columns represent the true classification while the rows represent the predicted classification. F) Top-10 variable importance for diagnosis classification according to the Mean Decrease Accuracy.

Supplementary figure 4. Association of the GD/GO gut microbiota with risk factors (gender and smoking). A) Heatmap of the significant association (blue boxes) between bacterial genera and gender (G) or smoking (S) in each diagnosis group (HC, GD and GO). In red, independent associations of the same genera with diagnosis (D: GD, GO and HC), eye-disease severity (E: no sign, mild and moderate-severe) or thyroid-status (T: hyperthyroid, euthyroid patients or euthyroid controls). B) *Bacteroides* spp. relative abundance decreased in current and ex smokers compared to never smokers in the GO group. P-values are from pairwise comparisons with Benjamini-Hochberg (FDR) correction.

Supplementary Figure 5. Bacterial genera differentially abundant amongst treatment groups at baseline: untreated (n=35), treated (n=70) and healthy controls (n=41). Heatmap of the median value of each genus per group, scaled according to the row Z-score. Only significant genera with P<0.05 from the linear regression model are shown; pairwise post-hoc with Benjamini-Hochberg (FDR) correction tests between groups are shown in the bar-plots.

Supplementary Figure 6: Analysis of the “GD-to-GO progression” associated microbiome. A) Schematic representation of the clinical history of two GD patients who developed GO during the project follow up. B) Extended bar-plots generated with STAMP testing differences at the genus level between GD and GO, individually. Differences at genus level between 1004-BL (GD) and 1004-EU (GO). C) Bar-plots representing difference at genus level of patient 1013-BL (GD) to 1013-EU (GO) (left) and from the 1013-EU (GO) to 1013-EFU (stable GO). Two samples-test was performed in STAMP using the G-test with Yates’ correction and Fisher’s with 95% confidence interval. Only genera with P value<0.05 were shown. D) *Bacteroides* spp. counts in the GD-to-GO transition. The two lines represent the 1004 and 1013 patients’ *Bacteroides* spp. Variation. The stars indicate the count of *Bacteroides* spp. related to the GO insurgence time point. In the background, the boxplots represent the *Bacteroides* spp. Distributions in each timepoint and in each group (whether controls, GD or GO).

Supplementary Table 1 Assays and ranges of normal value of serum TSH, free T4 and free T3 concentrations (first table) and anti TSH receptor antibody levels (second table) in different clinical centers.

CENTRE	THYROID HORMONES: REFERENCE RANGES				Anti TSH RECEPTOR ANTIBODY (UI/L)	
	ASSAY	TSH (mU/L)	FT4 (pmol/L)	FT3 (pmol/L)	ASSAY	REFERENCE RANGE
MILAN	ECLIA Roche Diagnostics	0.28 – 4.30	8.0 - 17.0	2.0 - 5.0	3rd generation TRAK test, BRAHMS TRAK human KRYPTOR, Thermo Fisher Scientific	positive > 1.5
CARDIFF	Abbott Architect	0.30 – 4.40	9.0 – 19.1	2.6 – 5.7	Roche Cobas platform	positive > 1.6
NEWCASTLE	Roche Cobas platform	0.30 - 4.70	9.5 – 21.5	3.5 - 6.5	Roche Cobas platform	positive > 1.0
ESSEN	Atellica IM Siemens	0.30 – 3.0	11.5 – 22.7	3.5- 6.5	Roche Cobas platform	positive > 1.75
BRUSSELS	ECLIA Roche Diagnostics	0.27 - 4.20	12.0 – 22.0	3.1 – 6.8	Competitive chemiluminescent assay, Kryptor compact plus, Thermofisher scientific	positive > 1.8